

Legal Overview

Human Genetics and Genomics: France

[WP2 – Human Genetics and Genomics]

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Executive Summary

Goal and approach

This report presents current legal regulation of human genetics and human genomics in France. Firstly, it presents an overview of the French legal system domestically and in relation to international legal obligations it is subject to. In the second part, it introduces an overview of current legal academic publications and legal developments in France. Finally, it presents specific legal considerations on this topic.

In order to present the key elements on human genetics and genomics in France, it focuses on six fundamental areas: (1) human germline gene editing, (2) genetic screening in general, (3) genetic testing in general, (4) prenatal testing and screening, (5) newborn screening, (6) advertising of genetic testing or screening. It addresses these six areas in the current legal debate (chapter 3), in recent legal developments (chapter 4), and finally in specific legal considerations (chapters 5 to 10).

Main Findings

The regulation of genetic in France appears in the civil code for general considerations and in the code for public health in relation to the medical use of genetics. The key legal instrument is the 1994 bioethics law, a law that has been revised in 2004 and 2011. This law defines the principles regarding the legal status of the human body in order to ensure the dignity of the person and requires the written consent before any genetic testing (art. 16-10 civil code). It also ensures the integrity of the human species as a whole (art. 16-4 of the civil code) and determines a juridical framework in relation to genetic testing in order to preserve the fundamental rights of the person. The 2004 revision of the bioethics law decided for a revision of the bioethics law every 5 years. The last revision process was initiated in 2018 with a large national debate organised by the National Ethics Consultative Committee (CCNE). Questions related to genetics and genomics have generated much interest as part of this public debate. The new bioethics law is expected to be voted in the first semester of 2019.

The emergence of new technologies, in particular CRISPR-Cas9, as well as new policy developments in France, in particular those detailed in the plan “Médecine France Génomique 2025” are fundamentally questioning the bioethics law.

There are a number of major official institutions overseeing issues related to human genetics and human genomics in France. The revision of the bioethics law in 2004 created the Biomedicine Agency and gave it a general mission in relation to genetics (according to art. L.1418-1 of the public health code). In addition, to the Biomedicine Agency, it is important to also recognise the role of the High Health Authority (HAS), the National Cancer Institute (INCa), and the National agency for the safety of drug and health products (ANSM).

Regarding the key issue of human germline gene editing, it is important to note that French law lacks clarity. Though it is clear that heritable genetic modifications are forbidden in the therapeutic context, it is unclear whether this interdiction also applies to the field of research. A number of scientific and policy groups, in particular the INSERM, the National Medical Academy, and the OPECST, support the use CRISPR-Cas9 on the human embryo for research purposes. However, in no way is the article 13 of the Oviedo Convention related to intervention on the human genome is being questioned.

More generally, this analysis of the legal regulation of human genetics and genomics in France points to a high concern on the part of legal and policy experts, as well as the general French public regarding the risk that the use of genomic technology might lead to eugenism; eugenism is massively rejected in France by both French experts and the population. Related to this general rejection of eugenism, some French legal experts, such as Jean-Pierre Delage, are promoting criminal sanctions against any activities that would take us closer to eugenism, such as the creation of transgenic embryos.

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Table 1 List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
CCNE	National Ethics Consultative Committee for the Life Sciences and Health (<i>Comité National Consultatif d’Ethique pour les sciences de la vie et de la santé</i>)
CNCB	French National Consultative Council for Biosecurity (<i>Le Conseil national consultatif pour la biosécurité français</i>)
CNIL	National Council for Information Technologies and Liberties (<i>Conseil National de l’Informatique et des Libertés</i>)
INSERM	National Institute of Health and medical Research (<i>Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale</i>)
GPA	Gestational surrogacy (<i>Gestation pour autrui</i>)
OPECST	Parliamentary Office for the Evaluation of Scientific and Technological Choices (<i>Office Parlementaire d’Evaluation des Choix Scientifiques et Technologiques</i>)
PMA	Medically-assisted reproduction (<i>Procréation médicalement assistée</i>)

Table 2 Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Genetic Test	A genetic test: is an assay performed to obtain genetic information (directly on DNA or even on other molecules (RNA, proteins), which by extension could give us genetic information.
Genetic Testing	<p>Genetic testing is usually offered to individual patients based on specific individual need on a one-on-one basis (diagnostic testing, prenatal testing, etc. https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/uses). An assay (a genetic test) would be conducted after the clinician has decided to prescribe the test to the specific patient in question.</p> <p>Genetic testing is a type of medical test that identifies changes in chromosomes, genes, or proteins. The results of a genetic test can confirm or rule out a suspected genetic condition or help determine a person’s chance of developing or passing on a genetic disorder.¹ Genetic testing could be accessed through a health care provider as part of clinical medical care, or as a service or product offered directly to consumers. Issues genetic testing raises relate to access rights, protection of integrity, medical oversight when these tests are being offered, as well as genetic counselling, and quality. Other questions that relate to genetic testing emerge in the area of</p>

¹ US National Library of Medicine, https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/genetic_testing, accessed 10 July 2018.

	<p>advertising and the use of genetic information. In regard to advertising such issues as, for example, whether genetic testing providers are or are not allowed to advertise their offered genetic tests emerge (contrast with a distinction being made for advertising prescription and non-prescription drugs).² In regard to genetic information, such issues as who can access one’s genetic information, and how this information could be used for different purposes, for example, life insurance. One of key issues that emerges in this regard is discrimination relating to one’s genome.</p>
<p>Genetic Screening</p>	<p>Genetic screening can have a few different meanings that differ based on subtle nuances and contexts, but in general, we contrast genetic screening from genetic testing because screening is offered to an entire group of people (not specific individuals). In particular screening cases, like newborn screening, for example, the screening programme follows public health frameworks (as opposed to genetic testing which is not a public health programme but within a clinical specialty; in countries where public health programmes don’t differ so strongly from clinical practice, you may want to ignore this if it confuses you more. Differences between public health programmes and clinical (one patient at a time) programmes could mean differences in how we approach consent and the obligatory nature of any programme). Other than the “group/population” aim of screening programmes, screening programmes can vary hugely in different ways: population/group targeted (population wide? Certain people/mothers at higher risks as a group?) etc.</p>
<p>Gene Editing/Genome Editing</p>	<p>Gene editing is a relatively recent term used for the description of modifying DNA (you may have previously heard in the past recombinant DNA technology or similar terms that all overlap in some fashion); the term gene editing has come along with the advent of particularly powerful and accurate tools like CRISPR-Cas9 (which is a tool that helps to change DNA). Gene editing can also be referred to as genome modification, which is more holistic, if you will as a concept, but addresses the same ideas; it basically includes not only changing individual DNA in one location but also many changes throughout the genome. One can edit genes in somatic cells (which are not inherited) or one could edit genes in gametes or germline cells which are inherited and would pass down, in theory, DNA modifications/edits to future generations.</p> <p>The term human genome germline modification then includes the modification of 1 or many bits of DNA in an inheritable human cell. Many authors also include the replacement of mitochondria from one embryo to another as a type of germline modification, though this can be argued as (not) being very distinct from DNA modification, for the sake of comparison with other studies, we will include it for the purposes of this SIENNA study.</p>

² Please consult Louiza Kalokairinou, Pascal Borry, Heidi Carmen Howard, Regulating the advertising of genetic tests in Europe: a balancing act, Journal of Medical Genetics, Volume 54, Issue 10.

Part I Introduction

1. National legal system in context

1.1 An overview of French legal system

France is a semi-presidential Republic. The current Republic is the fifth one; it started with a new Constitution on 4 October 1958. The Parliament, composed of the National Assembly (made of 577 deputies) and the Senate (made of 348 senators), holds legislative power. Sources of law in France are international and European treaties and conventions, constitutional and legislative rules, statutory instruments, and case laws.³ The highest norm is the Constitution⁴ which is composed of three fundamental instruments: the Constitution of the 4 October 1958, the Declaration for the rights of man and citizen of 1789, and the Preamble of the Constitution of the 27 October 1946.⁵ Since 1958, there have been 22 constitutional laws, i.e. laws that modify the constitution. Since 1971, the Constitutional council (*Conseil constitutionnel*) ensures that new laws conform with the Constitution. France is subject to international law obligations and is a signatory to numerous international treaties and conventions. According to Art. 55 of the French Constitution, international treaties ratified by France are superior to domestic legislation. Depending on the treaty at stake, it is either directly applicable to French law or needs to be transposed by an internal rule.

1.2 France and UN treaties and agencies

France is a member of the UN since its creation in 1945. It has joined several UN treaties that have relevance to the regulation of human genomics and human genetics, including the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)⁶ and the International Covenant on Social, Economic and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)⁷, both accessed on 4 November 1980.

France is a founding member of the UNESCO created in 1945. The UNESCO has drafted a series of Declaration of direct relevance to the regulation of genetics and genomics, including:

- Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights (2005);⁸
- Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights (1997);⁹

³ For more details about the French legal system, sources of law, and legislative process, see: https://e-justice.europa.eu/content_member_state_law-6-fr-en.do?member=1.

⁴ Constitution of the French Republic, accessible on the page of the National Assembly: http://www.assemblee-nationale.fr/connaissance/constitution.asp#P1_42

⁵ To this should also be added the Environment Charter of 2004.

⁶ UN Treaty Collection, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) and list of countries that are parties to the Covenant: https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?src=IND&mtdsg_no=IV-3&chapter=4&clang=en

⁷ UN Treaty Collection, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and list of countries that are parties to the Covenant : https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?chapter=4&clang=en&mtdsg_no=IV-4&src=IND

⁸ Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights: <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/bioethics-and-human-rights/>

⁹ Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genome-and-human-rights/>

- International Declaration on Human Genetic Data (2003).¹⁰

Furthermore, the 2015 report of the International Bioethics Committee (IBC) - “Reflection on the Human Genome and Human Rights” - published by the UNESCO is of particular relevance to the present inquiry on the regulation of human genetics and genomics.¹¹ However, it has to be noted that these regulations are soft laws, no binding instruments.

Finally, we may note that the World Health Organisation, of which France is a member state, has not made specific recommendations regarding human genomics and genetics.¹²

1.3 France and OECD

France became a member of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) on 7 August 1961.¹³ It has published a series of guidelines of direct relevance to the regulation of genetics and genomics, including:

- Guidelines for Human Biobanks and Genetic Research Databases;¹⁴
- Guidelines for Quality Assurance in Genetic Testing;¹⁵
- Guidelines for the Licensing of Genetic Inventions;¹⁶
- Pharmacogenetics;¹⁷
- Biomarkers and targeted therapies.¹⁸

1.4 France, Council of Europe, and EU law

France is a founding member of the Council of Europe. As a leading European human rights organisation, the Council has drafted several instruments related to the regulation of genetics and genomics, including:

¹⁰ International Declaration on Human Genetic Data: <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genetic-data/>

¹¹ UNESCO, International Bioethics Committee (IBC) - “Reflection on the Human Genome and Human Rights” (2015): http://unesdoc.unesco.org/Ulis/cgi-bin/ulis.pl?catno=233258&set=0058EB7442_3_128&gp=&lin=1&ll=c

¹² Jean-Yves Le Déaut et Catherine Procaccia, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les enjeux économiques, environnementaux, sanitaires et éthiques des biotechnologies à la lumière des nouvelles pistes de recherche »*, Paris, National Assembly and Senate, 2017, p. 102.

¹³ OECD, list of state members: <http://www.oecd.org/about/membersandpartners/list-oecd-member-countries.htm>

¹⁴ Guidelines for Human Biobanks and Genetic Research Databases <http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/guidelines-for-human-biobanks-and-genetic-research-databases.htm>

¹⁵ OECD Guidelines for Quality Assurance in Genetic Testing : <http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/oecdguidelinesforqualityassuranceingeneticstesting.htm>

¹⁶ OECD Guidelines for the Licensing of Genetic Inventions: <http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/guidelinesforthelicensingofgeneticinventions.htm>

¹⁷ OECD on Pharmacogenetics: <http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/pharmacogeneticsopportunitiesandchallengesforhealthinnovation.htm>

¹⁸ OECD on Biomarkers and targeted therapies <http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/biomarkersandtargetedtherapies.htm>

- the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), ratified by France on 3 May 1974;¹⁹
- the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine (Biomedicine Convention),²⁰ ratified by France on 13 December 2011, and its protocols, particularly, 2008 Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine Concerning Genetic Testing for Health Purposes (APGT).²¹ France signed it on 13 December 2011 but has not ratified it yet.
- A declaration by the bioethics committee on 2 December 2015 on genome edition technologies in which the Council reaffirms the principles 13 of the Oviedo Convention related to intervention on the human genome.

Similarly, the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights²² proclaimed on 7 December 2000 does not provide specific guidelines on this field beyond the right to integrity in art. 3.

2 Objectives, methodology and limitations of the report

2.1 Objectives

This report examines French regulatory responses to questions relating to genetics and genomics as specified in SIENNA Task 2.2. In particular, it seeks to address the following questions:

- Q 1 How, if at all, human germline gene editing is regulated?
- Q 2 Genetic screening in general
- Q 3 Genetic testing in general
- Q 4 Prenatal testing/screening
- Q 5 Newborn screening
- Q 6 Advertising of genetic testing or screening

2.2 Literature overview

This report draws from a literature review conducted on analyses produced by legal experts on human genetics and human genomics in France over the past five to ten years. It also proposes an analysis of the recent national legal scholarship in relation to this technology. For this research, the authors have conducted a desk-based review by going through various search engines, including google, the general catalogue of Sciences Po library and the online catalogue Dalloz which is the primary resource for legal scholarship in France. A variety of search terms were used including, “*génomique*”, “*génétique*”,

¹⁹ Council of Europe, European Convention on Human Rights: <https://www.echr.coe.int/Pages/home.aspx?p=basictexts/convention>. France Diplomatie, France and the European Court of Human Rights: <https://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/en/french-foreign-policy/international-justice/european-court-of-human-rights/>

²⁰ Council of Europe, Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine, <https://www.coe.int/en/web/bioethics/oviedo-convention> (hereinafter “Oviedo Convention”).

²¹ Council of Europe, Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine Concerning Genetic Testing for Health Purposes <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/203>

²² EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, http://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf

“*édition génomique*” associated with either “*droit*” (“law”) or “*régulation*”. Parts II and III present a synthesis of this research.

2.3 Limitations of this report

One of the challenges encountered in this task was the high focus in the current French debate with issues related to research on the embryo and the regulation of reproduction, in particular medically-assisted reproduction (PMA) and gestational surrogacy (GPA). As such, it was necessary to be vigilant to stay focus on the particular issues at stake for this present report and to avoid the research getting dominated by these related issues.

Another challenge in preparing this report is the very rapidly nature of the technology under study. This temporality means that it is difficult to find legal academic literature exploring very recent developments. However, reports published or commissioned by important political institutions, such as the Parliamentary Office for the Evaluation of Scientific and Technological Choices (OPECST) and the National Ethics Consultative Committee for the Life Sciences and Health (CCNE) have been particularly useful in preparing this report and contributed to partly filling this gap in terms of legal academic literature.

Part II current overview of legal academic publications and legal developments in France

3 Current legal academic debates in the area of genetics and genomics

3.1 Current legal academic debates regarding human germline gene editing

In France, there is debate between those who think there should be a moratorium regarding the modification of human germ cells and those who think that research on it should be allowed. Some support the interdiction by arguing that the use of this technology is not justified for medical reasons considering that cases of transmission of serious hereditary illnesses may be avoided through the use of the pre-implementation diagnosis.²³

Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag, a bioethics expert, observes that contrary to many other scientific discoveries, targeted modification of the genome has rapidly generated much debate from researchers and scientists, in particular in relation to a potential research calendar that could be put in place as well as an ethical international governance.²⁴ According to her, the solution proposed to adopt a moratorium in order to evaluate the technology as well as the societal consequences is not really

²³ J.-Y. Le Déaut et C. Procaccia, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les enjeux économiques, environnementaux, sanitaires et éthiques des biotechnologies à la lumière des nouvelles pistes de recherche »*, *op. cit.*, p. 74.

²⁴ Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag, « Médecine et génétique humaine. L'arbitrage juridique » dans Emmanuel Hirsch et François Hirsch (eds.), *Traité de bioéthique (IV) Les Nouveaux territoires de la bioéthique*, Paris, ERES, 2018, p. 200.

relevant in the French context.²⁵ Indeed, as she notes in an article published with other experts in the newspaper *Le Monde* in 2016, such moratorium on the clinical use of this technology does not seem pertinent considering the fact that such use is already forbidden in France in the current state of the law.²⁶

As Rial-Sebbag notes, using CRISPR-Cas9 on human embryo is forbidden according to art. 16-4 of the civil code. As she mentions, some experts have argued that this interdiction only applied to therapeutic application of CRISPR-Cas9 and, therefore, that the interdiction did not apply to the research in this area. However, Rial-Sebbag points to the fact that research is also regulated by the public health code in which, art. L. 2151-2 mentions that the “creation (for research purposes) of transgenic or chimeric embryos is forbidden”.²⁷ However, she notes that there is a lack of clarity regarding what should be understood by this interdiction, a lack of clarity that generates a “juridical insecurity for researchers regarding what they can or cannot do”.²⁸ For Rial-Sebbag and the authors of the piece published in *Le Monde* in 2016, research using the targeted engineering of the human embryo genome or human germ cells should be authorised within very strict legal boundaries. As they note, this would probably imply a change in the law.²⁹

The jurist Jean-Pierre Delage also discusses this article related to the interdiction of the creation of transgenic or chimeric embryos. However, he notes that this interdiction is problematical as it is not accompanied by any criminal sanction. He calls for the creation of such sanctions.³⁰ Furthermore, he points to the fact that there is a wide variety of responses to the creation of such embryos between countries. On this basis, though he recognises the difficult to do so, he suggests to develop an effective international bioethics criminal law.³¹

Relevant scientific and policy groups hold various positions in relation to the way the legal regulation of human germline gene editing should evolve. The list below presents the positions held by three of the most important of these groups in France. While they all support the interdiction to modify the human nuclear genome for reproductive purposes, they all also support the use of the CRISPR-Cas9 technology on the human embryo for research purposes.³²

- **The Ethics committee of the INSERM (National Institute of Health and Medical Research)**
 - o The INSERM ethics committee published a piece on CRISPR-Cas9 in which it makes five

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag et al., « Ingénierie du génome: il faut clarifier le cadre réglementaire », *Le Monde*, avril 2016p.

²⁷ Our translation. Original version: “la création (pour la recherche) d’embryons transgéniques ou chimériques est interdite”.

²⁸ E. Rial-Sebbag, « Médecine et génétique humaine. L’arbitrage juridique », art cit, p. 199-200.

²⁹ E. Rial-Sebbag et al., « Ingénierie du génome: il faut clarifier le cadre réglementaire », art cit.

³⁰ Jean-Pierre Delage, « L’interdiction de créer des embryons transgéniques ou chimériques », *Médecine et Droit*, 2012, p. 113. On this argument, see also: Pierre-Jérôme Delage, *Cybrides, transgènes et lois bioéthiques*, <https://droitetsf.hypotheses.org/34>, mai 2017, (consulté le 12 octobre 2018).

³¹ J.-P. Delage, « L’interdiction de créer des embryons transgéniques ou chimériques », art cit, p. 113.

³² Biomedicine Agency, *Information report to the Parliament and the Government*, s.l., Biomedicine Agency, 2017, p. 46.

- propositions among which it wishes to encourage research to evaluate the efficiency and safety of this technology, including on germline cells and embryos.³³
- It continues to be opposed to any modification of art. 13 of the Oviedo convention but proposes to “adapt the interdiction of any clinical application including genetic modifications on the germline, on a case-by-case basis for a restricted number of genetic diseases – the Huntington disease for instance – and suggests to put in place a European steering committee.”³⁴
 - It does not consider the idea of a moratorium to be a credible option because of the fact that it would be difficult to generate a strong international consensus for it.³⁵
- **National Medicine Academy:**
- In a 2016 report on genomic³⁶, it insisted on the need to maintain current legislation related to the interdiction to intervene on the structure of the DNA leading to a modification of the genome of the progeny but proposed to develop research using technology allowing the gene editing, including on human germ cells and embryo
 - It also proposed to adapt the law in relation to the interdiction to create transgenic embryos for research purposes, though confirming that such embryos would not be transferred in the uterus.³⁷
- **Report by the Parliamentary Office for the Evaluation of Scientific and Technological Choices (OPECST) (2017):**
- Argues that a voluntary moratorium such as the one of the Asilomar conference would be ineffective for technologies such as CRISPR-Cas9 considering the ease and the low cost of their use.³⁸
 - Argues that a moratorium in only some countries would also be ineffective as these technologies would be developed in other countries in any case and it would make the countries where the moratorium applies fall behind technologically.³⁹

³³ National Institute of Health and medical Research (INSERM) Ethics Committee, *Saisine concernant les questions liées au développement de la technologie CRISPR (clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeat)-Cas9*, s.l., National Institute of Health and medical Research (INSERM), 2016, p. 13.

³⁴ J.-Y. Le Déaut et C. Procaccia, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les enjeux économiques, environnementaux, sanitaires et éthiques des biotechnologies à la lumière des nouvelles pistes de recherche »*, *op. cit.*, p. 76. Our translation. Original version in French: “d’adapter l’interdiction de toute application clinique comportant des modifications génétiques sur la lignée germinale, au cas par cas pour un nombre réduit de maladies génétiques – par exemple, pour la maladie de Huntington – et suggère de mettre en place un comité de pilotage européen. Il entend promouvoir un débat ouvert sur les aspects sociétaux, avant une nécessaire déclinaison dans les législations nationales et internationales.”

³⁵ National Institute of Health and medical Research (INSERM) Ethics Committee, *Saisine concernant les questions liées au développement de la technologie CRISPR (clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeat)-Cas9*, *op. cit.*, p. 13.

³⁶ National Medicine Academy, *Modifications du génome des cellules germinales et de l'embryon humains*, s.l., National Medicine Academy, 2016.

³⁷ National Medicine Academy, *Modifications du génome des cellules germinales et de l'embryon humains*, s.l., National Medicine Academy, 2016.

³⁸ J.-Y. Le Déaut et C. Procaccia, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les enjeux économiques, environnementaux, sanitaires et éthiques des biotechnologies à la lumière des nouvelles pistes de recherche »*, *op. cit.*, p. 86.

³⁹ *Ibid.*

- According to the OPECST, fundamental research on gene editing should be encouraged in order to measure the effectiveness and safety of these techniques.⁴⁰
- It calls for the respect of art. 13 of the Oviedo Convention and for its extension to other countries. It also proposes to re-examine art. 13 once research on germline gene editing will be more advanced. It believes that once this technology will be safer, therapeutic tests could be examined on a case by case basis to cure a patient of a incurable hereditary illness.⁴¹
- It also recommends the creation of a sort of “IPCC” for gene editing and a strong involvement of the WHO, the UNESCO and the Council of Europe in relation to this technology.⁴²

3.2 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic screening in general

None identified.

3.3 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic testing in general

As some experts note, the question of secondary findings is particularly problematic in the context of French law related to information given to family members of genetic results. According to decree 2013-527, the person is informed prior to the genetic testing of the obligation to inform his/her family members should a serious genetic anomaly was found, as long as preventive measures and therapy are available. Though an individual is free to decide whether or not to receive results, there is an obligation to transmit the results to the family members. Hence, contrary to the person who conducts the testing, they have no right to know.⁴³

Furthermore, the jurist Anna Pigeon points to the fact that some weaknesses in the current state of the law may be noted in relation to the information provided to the patient prior to a test. Indeed, though the law makes it clear, according to decree of the 27 May 2013, that the person must be informed of the risk to identify genetic characteristics unrelated to the prescription, this specification only partially addressed questions posed by genetic testing as raised in the preparatory works for the revision of the bioethics law in 2011. For instance, what is to be done with data that have an uncertain meaning at the time of the diagnostic but that may make sense later on with the developments of science?⁴⁴

Pigeon insists on the need to more specifically define the three categories of information that may be discovered by the sequencing of the genome so that the patient may take an informed decision concerning his or her right to know or not to know. The three categories she distinguishes are the

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 87-88.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, p. 103-104.

⁴² *Ibid.*

⁴³ Bertrand Isidor, Mathilde Nizon et Marie Vincent, « Données secondaires: un enjeu scientifique et éthique » dans Emmanuel Hirsch et François Hirsch (eds.), *Traité de bioéthique (IV) Les Nouveaux territoires de la bioéthique*, Paris, ERES, 2018, p. 267-268.

⁴⁴ Anna Pigeon, « Les enjeux de l'utilisation des technologies de séquençage du génome dans le cadre du soin », *Cahiers Droit, Sciences & Technologies*, 2015, vol. 5, sect. 12 and 16. Our translation from the original in French.

following:

- “the information could have a clinical consequence and have no relation with the indication of the prescription but may not benefit from any preventive measures, treatments or genetic counselling”;
- “the information could have a known clinical consequence and have no relation with the indication of the prescription but may benefit from any preventive measures, treatments or genetic counselling”;
- “a variation of the genome is discovered but it is not known whether this variation is pathogenic or not.”⁴⁵

Furthermore, some argue that the right of each individual to have access to the knowledge of his/her DNA should be recognised and that the current criminal prohibition to conduct genetic testing beyond any medical context should be lifted.⁴⁶

3.4 Current legal academic debates regarding prenatal testing/screening

There are concerns that the generalisation of high throughput sequencing leads the society closer to the possibility for parents to choose babies of the highest “quality” possible. This risk is raised in the Parliamentary report on genetics published in 2014.⁴⁷ Professor Bertrand Jordan also highlights this risk in an article entitled “on the way to the perfect child!”.⁴⁸

3.5 Current legal academic debates regarding newborn screening

None identified.

3.6 Current legal academic debates regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening

There is much concern in France in relation to the existence of genetic tests freely accessible online outside any juridical regulation. A number of publications from legal experts point to this concern.⁴⁹

⁴⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 14, 15, and 16.

⁴⁶ Camille Bourdaine-Mignot et Tatiana Gründler, « Examens génétiques et médecine génomique : pour le maintien du cadre juridique existant », *La Revue des droits de l'homme*, août 2018.

⁴⁷ Alain Claeys et Jean-Sébastien Vialatte, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les progrès de la génétique: vers une médecine de précision? Les enjeux scientifiques, technologiques, sociaux et éthiques de la médecine personnalisées »*, Paris, National Assembly and Senate, 2014, p. 124.

⁴⁸ Bertrand Jordan, « Chroniques génomiques. En route vers l'enfant parfait! », *médecine/sciences*, 2013, vol. 29, p. 665-668.

⁴⁹ Vélizara Anastasova et Emmanuel Rial-Sebbag, « Les tests génétiques en accès libre: quelle protection pour le consommateur européen? », *Revue de droit sanitaire et social*, 2012, n° 5, p. 817-827. RIAL-SEBBAG, E. 2012. « Protection juridique des usagers de tests génétiques en accès libre, une protection nécessaire ? », dans Actes table ronde, Accès aux tests génétiques en Europe : droit et protection des utilisateurs, *Revue générale de droit médical*, n° 42. Pascal Ducournau, Pierre-Antoine Gourraud, Emmanuelle Rial-Sebbag, Alexandre Bulle et Anne Cambon- Thomsen, “Tests génétiques en accès libre sur Internet - Stratégies commerciales et enjeux éthiques et sociétaux”, *médecine/sciences*, 2011, 27 (1) 95). See also Anne-Laure Lebrun, « Tests génétiques : le business de l'ADN », *Le Figaro*, 11 May 2018. Accessible online at : <http://sante.lefigaro.fr/article/tests-genetiques-le-business-de-l-adn/> (accessed 29 November 2018).

4 Legal developments in the area of genetics and genomics

4.1 Overview of relevant laws

The main French texts relevant to the legal regulation of human genetics and human genomics are the following:

- Law n° 94-653 of the 29 July 1994 related to respect of the human body (as modified in 2004 and 2011);⁵⁰
- Law n° 94-654 of the 29 July 1994 related to the donation and the use of human body elements and products, to medical assistance for procreation and prenatal screening;⁵¹
- Law n° 2012-300 of the 5 March 2012 related to research involving the human person;⁵²
- Order of the 27 May 2013 defining rules of good practices applicable to a person's genetic testing for medical aims.⁵³

The regulation of genetic in France appear in the civil code for general considerations and in the code for public health in relation to medical use of genetics. The key legal instrument for the regulation of genetics and genomics in France is the 1994 bioethics law, a law that has seen several revisions since its creation, in particular in 2004 and in 2011. It defines the principles regarding the legal status of the human body in order to ensure the dignity of the person and requires the written consent before any genetic testing (art. 16-10 civil code) and of the integrity of the human species as a whole (art. 16-4 of the civil code). It also determines a juridical framework in relation to genetic testing in order to preserve the fundamental rights of the person. The drafting of this text in 1994 gave France a key role in the drafting of the Oviedo Convention in 1997.⁵⁴

The bioethics law was revised in 2004 with the law n° 2004-800 related to bioethics. This law established the Biomedicine Agency (*Agence de biomédecine*) and decided for a revision of the bioethics law every 5 years. Hence, the bioethics law was revised again in 2011 with the law n° 2011-814 of the 7 July 2011.⁵⁵ The last revision process was initiated in 2018 with a large national debate

⁵⁰ Accessible online at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000549619&dateText>

⁵¹ Accessible online at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000549618&dateText>

⁵² Accessible online at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000025441587>

⁵³ Accessible online at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000027513617&categorieLien=id>

⁵⁴ National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Réflexion éthique sur l'évolution des tests génétiques liée au séquençage de l'ADN humain à très haut débit*. Avis n° 124, s.l., CCNE, 2016, p. 25.

⁵⁵ These details come from the brief history of the bioethics law presented on the Documentation Française website: <http://www.ladocumentationfrancaise.fr/dossiers/bioethique/historique-lois-bioethique.shtml> (accessed 15 October 2018).

organised by the National Ethics Consultative Committee (CCNE).⁵⁶ Questions related to genetics and genomics have generated much interest as part of this public debate. After the topic of procreation, it is the theme that occupied most of the debates organised in French regions.⁵⁷

The emergence of new technologies, in particular CRISPR-Cas9, as well as new policy developments in France, in particular those detailed in the plan “Médecine France Génomique 2025” (produced by AVIESAN in 2015) are fundamentally questioning the bioethics law. As such, the juridical framework currently regulating generics and genomics in France is evolving. The new bioethics law is expected to be voted in the first semester of 2019. Some of key questions related to the legal regulation of the genetics and genomics as part of the national debate that took place in relation to the revision process of the law of bioethics in 2018 are of particular interest to this section and will be highlighted in the following pages.⁵⁸

There are a number of major official institutions overseeing issues related to human genetics and human genomics in France. The revision of the bioethics law in 2004 created the Biomedicine Agency and gave it a general mission in relation to genetics (according to art. L.1418-1 of the public health code). It was due to draft a set of “good practices applicable to the prescription and the conduct of a person’s genetic testing and of his/her identification through genetic stamp for medical aims (art. L.1131-2 of the same code), as well as to play a role in leading the reflection on genetic.⁵⁹ In addition to the Biomedicine Agency, for the oversight over genetics and genomics in France, it is important to also recognise the role of the High Health Authority (HAS), the National Cancer Institute (INCa), and the National agency for the safety of drug and health products (ANSM) for quality control of medical dispositives because, according to texts, genetic tests are recognised as *in vitro* diagnostic medical devices.⁶⁰

4.2 Legal developments regarding human germline gene editing

Article 40 of the law 2011-814 of the 7 July 2011 related to bioethics, added a new paragraph to the art. L. 2151-2 of the public health code according to which: “The creation of transgenic or chimeric embryos is forbidden.” However, as Jean-Pierre notes, this interdiction is rather weak as it does not come with any criminal sanctions.⁶¹

The question related to human germline gene editing has been raised as part of the national debate that took place in 2018 to prepare the revision of the bioethics law. The CCNE asked: “Should genetic engineering of the embryo be allowed within a strict framework in order to better understand the

⁵⁶ The public debate was centralised by a website: “Bioéthique: Etats généraux 2018”: <https://etatsgenerauxdelabioethique.fr> (accessed 15 October 2018).

⁵⁷ C. Bourdaine-Mignot et T. Gründler, « Examens génétiques et médecine génomique : pour le maintien du cadre juridique existant », art cit, p. 1.

⁵⁸ National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Bioéthique Etats généraux. Rapport de synthèse du Comité Consultatif National d’Ethique. Opinions du comité citoyen*, s.l., CCNE, 2018, p. 32-33.

⁵⁹ A. Claeys et J.-S. Vialatte, *Rapport au nom de l’Office parlementaire d’évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les progrès de la génétique: vers une médecine de précision? Les enjeux scientifiques, technologiques, sociaux et éthiques de la médecine personnalisées »*, op. cit., p. 113.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*

⁶¹ J.-P. Delage, « L’interdiction de créer des embryons transgéniques ou chimériques », art cit, p. 111.

development of some pathologies, without, nonetheless, in the current stage of the sciences, consider the re-implantation of the genetically modified embryos?"⁶² In no way does this question concerns the possibility to modify the progeny of a person which is forbidden according to the art. 16-4 of the civil code that states that "there may be no transformation of genes in order to alter the descent of a person."⁶³

As already mentioned in the previous section of this report, Rial-Sebbag points to the fact that there is a lack of clarity in relation to the modification of gene in the embryo for research purposes. Though it is clear that such heritable genetic modification is forbidden in the therapeutic context; it is unclear whether this interdiction also applies to the field of research.⁶⁴

Another aspect that the rapporteurs of the 2017 OPECST report suggest to address at part of the 2018 revision process of the bioethics law is the transfer of mitochondria DNA.⁶⁵

4.3 Legal developments regarding genetic screening in general

None identified.

4.4 Legal developments regarding genetic testing in general

A noteworthy legal development regarding genetic testing is the 27 May 2013 decree defining the rules of good practices applicable to the evaluation of genetic characteristics of a person for medical purposes. It has been elaborated by the Biomedicine Agency together with the High Health Authority. It reminds that the person should remain at the centre of concern, defines the way results should be delivered, in particular in relation to incidental findings. It also insists on the fact that results have consequences also for the family members of the patient.⁶⁶

Another noteworthy recent legal development in relation to genetic testing concerns the law related to research involving the human person adopted in 2012 and that came into effect in 2016: this law lifted some of the requirements concerning written consent in case of the reuse for research of genetic material obtained within the clinical context. It is now allowed that research be carried out simply on

⁶² National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Bioéthique Etats généraux. Rapport de synthèse du Comité Consultatif National d'Éthique. Opinions du comité citoyen*, op. cit., p. 32-33. Faut-il permettre des recherches d'ingénierie génomique sur l'embryon, dans un cadre précis, afin de mieux comprendre le développement de certaines pathologies, toutefois, sans envisager, en l'état de la science, la réimplantation d'embryons génétiquement modifiés ?

⁶³ Original version in French: "aucune transformation ne peut être apportée aux caractères génétiques dans le but de modifier la descendance d'une personne."

⁶⁴ E. Rial-Sebbag, « Médecine et génétique humaine. L'arbitrage juridique », art cit, p. 199-200.

⁶⁵ J.-Y. Le Déaut et C. Procaccia, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les enjeux économiques, environnementaux, sanitaires et éthiques des biotechnologies à la lumière des nouvelles pistes de recherche »*, op. cit., p. 112.

⁶⁶ A. Claeys et J.-S. Vialatte, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les progrès de la génétique: vers une médecine de précision? Les enjeux scientifiques, technologiques, sociaux et éthiques de la médecine personnalisées »*, op. cit., p. 113.

the basis of the absence of objection from the person.⁶⁷

Furthermore, a 2002 law had been put in place to forbid any discrimination based on genetics and to ban insurance to ask their clients to proceed with a genetic testing. As part of the recent national consultation related to the revision of the bioethics law, a proposition has been formulated to add to the law the interdiction for banks, insurances, and employers to ask individuals whether they have already carried out a genetic test and, even more so, to give them the results.⁶⁸

Another question that has been raised as part of the 2018 national consultation for the revision of the bioethics law concerns what is to be done regarding the increasing possibility of obtaining incidental findings from the sequencing of the genome.⁶⁹

The 2011 revision of the bioethics law also slightly modified the law related to information to family members.⁷⁰ Indeed, transmission to the family may either be done by the patient him or herself or go through the prescribing doctor, should the patient prefer to do so.⁷¹

One of the recommendations formulated by the rapporteurs of the Parliamentary report published in 2014 on genetics is for France to ratify the additional protocol of the Convention of Human Rights and Biomedicine Concerning Genetic Testing for Health Purposes (APGT).⁷² Indeed, while France signed it on 13 December 2011, it has not ratified it yet.⁷³

4.5 Legal developments regarding prenatal testing/screening

Prenatal screening of Down syndrome is authorised from the analysis of foetal DNA circulating in the maternal blood. One of the questions raised by the 2018 national debate as part of the revision of the bioethics law concerns whether this technique should be extended to the screening of other forms of aneuploidy.⁷⁴

The current debate also concerns screening before conception. At the moment in France, this screening only concerns couples with particular risks of transmitting monogenic heritable illnesses. It

⁶⁷ E. Rial-Sebbag, « Médecine et génétique humaine. L'arbitrage juridique », art cit, p. 196-197.

⁶⁸ C. Bourdaine-Mignot et T. Gründler, « Examens génétiques et médecine génomique : pour le maintien du cadre juridique existant », art cit, p. 3. It is important to specify that this is not the position of the authors of this article but a position that they report and that they radically disagree with.

⁶⁹ National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Bioéthique Etats généraux. Rapport de synthèse du Comité Consultatif National d'Ethique. Opinions du comité citoyen*, op. cit., p. 32-33.

⁷⁰ J.-Y. Le Déaut et C. Procaccia, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les enjeux économiques, environnementaux, sanitaires et éthiques des biotechnologies à la lumière des nouvelles pistes de recherche »*, op. cit., p. 112.

⁷¹ A. Pigeon, « Les enjeux de l'utilisation des technologies de séquençage du génome dans le cadre du soin », art cit, p. 18.

⁷² <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/203>

⁷³ A. Claeys et J.-S. Vialatte, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les progrès de la génétique: vers une médecine de précision? Les enjeux scientifiques, technologiques, sociaux et éthiques de la médecine personnalisées »*, op. cit., p. 159.

⁷⁴ National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Bioéthique Etats généraux. Rapport de synthèse du Comité Consultatif National d'Ethique. Opinions du comité citoyen*, op. cit., p. 32-33.

is conducted once a case has been identified in the family. Such test could be extended to all couples, even those for whom no particular risk has been identified.⁷⁵ The Citizen committee constituted as part of the 2018 national debate for the revision of the bioethics law is in favour of giving access to this test to all those who may wish it.⁷⁶

In 2009, the National Ethics Committee for Health and Life Sciences (CCNE) published an opinion piece (n°107) in which it suggests, in the case of a pre-implantation diagnosis of the embryo in vitro, to conduct a karyotype in order to detect a potential Down syndrome, rather than waiting to conduct the prenatal screening on the pregnant woman. However, this suggestion has not been retained by the legislator.⁷⁷

Another aspect that the rapporteurs of the 2017 OPECST report suggest to address as part of the 2018 revision process of the bioethics law is the possibility of examining, during a pre-implantation diagnostic, illnesses caused by genetic or metabolic characteristics for high risk groups, or possibilities to preserve oocytes.⁷⁸

4.6 Legal developments regarding newborn screening

One of the questions raised as part of the 2018 national consultation for the revision of the bioethics law is whether screening of newborn should be authorised for known causal mutations of genetic diseases, or even, the sequencing of the genome.⁷⁹

4.7 Legal developments regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening

None identified.

4.8 Legal developments regarding genetic data

The status of genetic data is an important topic in France. The law has addressed it in its 2004 revision of the 1978 law on information technology and liberties by creating a particular regime for the treatment of genetic data, including outside the area of medical research. Their use requires an authorisation from the National Council for Information Technologies and Liberties (CNIL), except when used for prevention, medical diagnostics or treatments.⁸⁰

⁷⁵ National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Réflexion éthique sur l'évolution des tests génétiques liée au séquençage de l'ADN humain à très haut débit*. Avis n° 124, op. cit., p. 39.

⁷⁶ C. Bourdaine-Mignot et T. Gründler, « Examens génétiques et médecine génomique : pour le maintien du cadre juridique existant », art cit.

⁷⁷ National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Réflexion éthique sur l'évolution des tests génétiques liée au séquençage de l'ADN humain à très haut débit*. Avis n° 124, op. cit., p. 70.

⁷⁸ J.-Y. Le Déaut et C. Procaccia, *Rapport au nom de l'Office parlementaire d'évaluation des choix scientifiques et technologiques sur « Les enjeux économiques, environnementaux, sanitaires et éthiques des biotechnologies à la lumière des nouvelles pistes de recherche »*, op. cit., p. 112.

⁷⁹ National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Bioéthique Etats généraux. Rapport de synthèse du Comité Consultatif National d'Éthique. Opinions du comité citoyen*, op. cit., p. 32-33.

⁸⁰ David Gruson, « Pour une régulation positive de l'intelligence artificielle en génétique » dans Emmanuel Hirsch et François Hirsch (eds.), *Traité de bioéthique (IV) Les Nouveaux territoires de la bioéthique*, Paris, ERES, 2018,

Part III Specific legal considerations on human genetics and genomics

5 Human germline gene editing

As already mentioned above in the present report, French law lacks clarity with regards to research on human germline gene editing. Related to this lack of clarity, the Biomedical Agency has no research protocols to modify the genome of the human embryo.⁸¹

For further legal considerations on human germline gene editing, please see sections 3.1 and 4.2 that present the key elements on this topic.

6 Genetic screening in general

Genetic screening in France is only prenatal and is therefore discussed in the section 8 below on “Prenatal testing/screening”.

7 Genetic testing in general

It is important to note that, as the jurist Elsa Supiot has shown, a “genetic exceptionnalism” can be observed in the French legal system.⁸² As the CCNE puts it, this is justified by the fact that it is less a medicine of the ill person than a medicine aiming at identifying the illness.⁸³ Furthermore, this exceptionnalism is also justified by the fact that the results of the testing may have implications for other people, i.e. the patient’s family members.

The law regulates situations in which conditions genetic testing may be prescribed, the way they should be conducted, as well as the delivery of results. Most of the relevant dispositions were introduced in the bioethics law of 2004 and were slightly modified by the 2011 law. They appear in 16-10 to 16-13 of the civil code and in the public health code, art. L. 1131-1 and following. Art. 16-10 of the civil code defines the finalities for which a genetic test may be conducted and the modalities of the consent that it required. Since the law no. 2002-303 of the 4 March 2002, information is a right of the patient. This information includes his/her state, the proposed treatments, their usefulness and necessity, and the risks involved. Treatments require the free and informed consent of the person and this consent may be withdrawn at any point in time (art. L. 1111-4 al. 4 of the public health code).

p. 564. The CNIL published in 2017 a book on genetic data: CNIL, *Les données génétiques*, Paris, La documentation française, 2017.

⁸¹ Hervé Chneiweiss quoted in *La Croix*, “Modification du génome, l’urgence d’une régulation internationale”, 27 November 2018, accessible online at: <https://www.la-croix.com/Sciences-et-ethique/Ethique/Modification-genome-lurgence-dune-regulation-internationale-2018-11-26-1200985648> (accessed on 28 November 2018).

⁸² National Ethics Consultative Committee for life and health sciences (CCNE), *Réflexion éthique sur l’évolution des tests génétiques liée au séquençage de l’ADN humain à très haut débit*. Avis n° 124, *op. cit.*, p. 62.

⁸³ *Ibid.*

Further details related to consent in genetic testing are provided in art. R. 1135-4 et R. 1131-5 (last paragraph) of the health public code.

Art. L. 1131-1 and following of the public health code remind the modalities for acquiring informed consent, in writing, and the information that the person must be provided in advance of the test. It also gives the Biomedicine Agency competence to determine the practitioners allowed to conduct such test. The law of 2011 imposed transmitting information to the family members potentially concerned by the results of genetic testing in case of the detection of a severe genetic anomaly whose consequences might be prevented and organised an anonymous procedure through the doctor in case the patient did not want to know the results. This appears in art. L. 1131-1-2 of the public health code.

In the order of the 27 May 2013 defining rules of good practices applicable to a person's genetic testing for medical aims, the Biomedicine Agency together with High Health Authority remind that the individual must remain at the centre of concern, that a high attention must be give to the information provided to the patient and to his/her consent, and define the way results must be delivered, in particular in cases where there are incidental discoveries resulting from the test.

In case of violations of these regulations, criminal sanctions apply as defined in the criminal code, art. 225-25 and following.

For further legal considerations on genetic testing, please see sections 3.3 and 4.4 above.

8 Prenatal testing/screening

The relevant articles in French law related to the identification of genetic diseases in prenatal diagnostic are art. L. 2131-1 to L. 2131-5 of the public health code. Prenatal diagnosis has firstly been authorised by law n°94-654 of the 29 July 1994 in order to detect particularly serious illnesses *in utero* in the embryo or the foetus.⁸⁴ It is conducted in multidisciplinary centres for prenatal diagnosis. As the CCNE notes, the conditions in which this test is conducted has massively evolved over the past 20 years. Indeed, while it initially only concerned couples who had already had a child with Down syndrome, the diagnosis was then extended to certain categories of women (in particular those who were over 38 years old) and was finally conducted as a screening.⁸⁵ Good practices related to prenatal screening and diagnosis of Down syndrome with the use of maternal serum markers are defined in the degree of the 23 June 2009. While newborn screening of cystic fibrosis exists in France since 2002 to ensure that care be provided as soon as possible, prenatal screening is forbidden.⁸⁶

For further legal considerations on prenatal testing/screening, please see sections 3.4 and 4.5 above.

9 Newborn screening

Newborn screening for five illnesses is free and systematically proposed. It requires the parents' concern. This screening primarily concerns genetic illnesses: phenylketonuria, congenital adrenal

⁸⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 69.

⁸⁵ *Ibid.*

⁸⁶ *Ibid.*

hyperplasia, sickle cell disease, and cystic fibrosis. As mentioned above, through prenatal screening of cystic fibrosis for newborn screening of cystic fibrosis is forbidden, newborn screening for this illness exists in France since 2002 to ensure that care be provided as soon as possible.⁸⁷

10 Advertising of genetic testing or screening

Nothing specific to note apart from the fact that, as mentioned in section 3.6, the availability of genetic testing online violates French law. Indeed, results of genetic testing in France need to be delivered together with appropriate medical advice. See references provided in the footnote 49 related to section 3.6 of this report.

Part VI Discussion and conclusion

11 Discussion and conclusion

The regulation of genetic in France appears in the civil code for general considerations and in the code for public health in relation to the medical use of genetics. The key legal instrument is the 1994 bioethics law, a law that has been revised in 2004 and 2011. This law defines the principles regarding the legal status of the human body in order to ensure the dignity of the person and requires the written consent before any genetic testing (art. 16-10 civil code). It also ensures the integrity of the human species as a whole (art. 16-4 of the civil code) and determines a juridical framework in relation to genetic testing in order to preserve the fundamental rights of the person. The 2004 revision of the bioethics law decided for a revision of the bioethics law every 5 years. The last revision process was initiated in 2018 with a large national debate organised by the National Ethics Consultative Committee (CCNE). Questions related to genetics and genomics have generated much interest as part of this public debate. The new bioethics law is expected to be voted in the first semester of 2019.

The emergence of new technologies, in particular CRISPR-Cas9, as well as new policy developments in France, in particular those detailed in the plan “Médecine France Génomique 2025” are fundamentally questioning the bioethics law.

There are a number of major official institutions overseeing issues related to human genetics and human genomics in France. The revision of the bioethics law in 2004 created the Biomedicine Agency and gave it a general mission in relation to genetics (according to art. L.1418-1 of the public health code). In addition, to the Biomedicine Agency, it is important to also recognise the role of the High Health Authority (HAS), the National Cancer Institute (INCa), and the National agency for the safety of drug and health products (ANSM).

Regarding the key issue of human germline gene editing, it is important to note that French law lacks clarity. Though it is clear that heritable genetic modifications are forbidden in the therapeutic context, it is unclear whether this interdiction also applies to the field of research. A number of scientific and policy groups, in particular the INSERM, the National Medical Academy, and the OPECST, support the

⁸⁷ *Ibid.*

use CRISPR-Cas9 on the human embryo for research purposes. However, in no way is the article 13 of the Oviedo Convention related to intervention on the human genome is being questioned.

More generally, this analysis of the legal regulation of human genetics and genomics in France points to a high concern on the part of legal and policy experts, as well as the general French public regarding the risk that the use of genomic technology might lead to eugenism; eugenism is massively rejected in France by both French experts and the population. Related to this general rejection of eugenism, some French legal experts, such as Jean-Pierre Delage, are promoting criminal sanctions against any activities that would take us closer to eugenism, such as the creation of transgenic embryos.

References

Legal texts

International treaties, conventions and guidelines by international organisations

International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights:
https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?src=IND&mtdsg_no=IV-3&chapter=4&clang=en

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights:
https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?chapter=4&clang=en&mtdsg_no=IV-4&src=IND

Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights: <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/bioethics-and-human-rights/>

Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights
<http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genome-and-human-rights/>

International Declaration on Human Genetic Data: <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/bioethics/human-genetic-data/>

EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, http://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf

UNESCO, International Bioethics Committee (IBC) - “Reflection on the Human Genome and Human Rights” (2015): http://unesdoc.unesco.org/ulis/cgi-bin/ulis.pl?catno=233258&set=0058EB7442_3_128&gp=&lin=1&ll=c

OECD Guidelines for Human Biobanks and Genetic Research Databases
<http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/guidelines-for-human-biobanks-and-genetic-research-databases.htm>

OECD Guidelines for Quality Assurance in Genetic Testing :
<http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/oecdguidelinesforqualityassuranceingeneticstesting.htm>

OECD Guidelines for the Licensing of Genetic Inventions:
<http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/guidelinesforthelicensingofgeneticinventions.htm>

OECD on Pharmacogenetics:
<http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/pharmacogeneticsopportunitiesandchallengesforhealthinnovation.htm>

OECD on Biomarkers and targeted therapies:
<http://www.oecd.org/sti/biotech/biomarkersandtargetedtherapies.htm>

European Convention on Human Rights:
<https://www.echr.coe.int/Pages/home.aspx?p=basictexts/convention>

Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine, <https://www.coe.int/en/web/bioethics/oviedo-convention> (“Oviedo Convention”).

Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine Concerning Genetic Testing for Health Purposes <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/203>

National law

Constitution of the French Republic:

http://www.assemblee-nationale.fr/connaissance/constitution.asp#P1_42

The main national legal text in relation to the regulation of genomic and genetic in France is the Bioethics law that was first created in 1994 and that has gone through several revisions since then, in 2004 (with the law n° 2004-800), 2011 (with the law n° 2011-814) and 2013 (with the law n° 2013-715). It is expected to be revised again in 2019. It includes:

- the law n° 94-653 of the 29 July 1994 related to respect of the human body:
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000549619&dateText>
- the Law n° 94-654 of the 29 July 1994 related to the donation and the use of human body elements and products, to medical assistance for procreation and prenatal screening:
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000549618&dateText>

Relevant texts also include:

- Law n° 78-17 on information technology and liberties:
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000886460>
- Law n° 2002-303 of 4 March 2002 related to the rights of patients and to the quality of the healthcare system:
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000227015&categorieLien=id>
- Law n° 2012-300 of the 5 March 2012 related to research involving the human person:
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000025441587>
- Decree (*Arrêté*) of the 27 May 2013 defining rules of good practices applicable to a person’s genetic testing for medical aims:
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000027513617&categorieLien=id>
- Decree (*Décret*) n° 2013-527 of 20 June 2013 on the condition of information of family members in the context of a genetic testing for medical purpose:
<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/eli/decret/2013/6/20/AFSP1311381D/jo/texte>

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